

Demographic Dynamics in Latin America (1961–2023): A Characterization using Functional Biplots and Neutrosophic TOPSIS Neutrosophic TOPSIS

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Abstract: This study analyzes the Growth Rate behavior Demographic (TDC) of the countries Latin Americans during the period 1961–2023 through Methods Multivariate Functional and Neutrosophic TOPSIS. The techniques descriptive, grouping functional and display using Functional Biplot allowed identify curves of countries with behavior atypical (Venezuela, Uruguay, Honduras) and group countries with patterns similar in different points in the period studied. The integration of TOPSIS Neutrosophic modeled uncertainty in key factors such as policies internal, migration and access to family planning, classifying countries according to his performance demographic. The results reveal a decrease sustained TDC over 63 years in the region, with a variance explained by 87% Component Analysis Main Functional (FPCA), highlighting milestones as changes in policies internal and external and the effects of migration, framed in the context economic, political and social of each country.

Keywords: Functional Data, Growth Rate Population, Latin America, Functional Biplot, Neutrosophic TOPSIS

1. Introduction

Technological advances in medicine since the 1970s led to a significant increase in child survival rates and adult life expectancy. This resulted in higher population growth rates in all countries, disproportionately affecting developing countries. However, this rapid population growth raised concerns: How could initiatives aimed at boosting economic growth and lifting people out of poverty be sustained when the population was growing at such a dramatic rate? [1]. Today, more than half a century later, the trend has reversed. The population growth rate is declining annually in most countries of the world, including those in the developing world [2], where birth rates had historically been significantly higher. Latin America has undergone profound transformations in recent decades, marked by a marked reduction in fertility rates and significant changes in the age structure of the population. This phenomenon stems from family planning policies and improved access to contraceptive methods, which have empowered women to make autonomous decisions about their fertility, thus contributing to a gradual and substantial decline in birth rates [2]. According to recent estimates by the United Nations (2019), the region will experience sustained population growth peaking in 2058 at approximately 767.5 million people, followed by a subsequent decline driven mainly by persistently low fertility rates and an aging population [3].

These demographic dynamics require approaching and analyzing statistical techniques that allow for a deep and multidimensional understanding of temporal observations. Functional Multivariate Analysis (FMA) emerges in this context as a particularly powerful tool. Unlike traditional statistical methods, which are based on discrete data points, FMA treats the entire function observed over time as its fundamental unit of analysis, allowing for a comprehensive and continuous study of the investigated phenomena [4]. Among the FMA methods, Functional Principal Component Analysis (FPCA) stands out. This method allows for an effective reduction in the dimensionality of functional data while preserving a high proportion of the original information. Furthermore, FPCA facilitates the identification of essential patterns in population behavior over time [5]. Techniques such as K-means functional clustering further allow for the classification and recognition of groups of countries with similar demographic dynamics in different regions, which can subsequently be characterized [6]. A novel visualization technique, the Functional Biplot, is also introduced. This method proposes to use only the eigenfunction associated with capturing the greatest variability, allowing the simultaneous visualization of individual observations and the main function that characterizes the trajectory of the variable, defined by the maximum variability captured by FPCA [10].

This study employs Functional Multivariate Analysis techniques combined with Neutrosophic Topsis to analyze the population growth rate (PGR) of Latin American countries during the period 1961–2023. The use of these techniques allows for the continuous and joint observation of the evolution of the PGR, including its fluctuations and changes driven by the internal and external policies of each country, as well as migration effects, modeling the uncertainty in these factors through Neutrosophic Topsis. The results reveal a sustained decline in the population growth rate between 1962 and 2022, with an explained variance of 87% using FPCA, and extraordinary events such as those that affected Cuba and El Salvador in the early 1990s. In addition, the study highlights the extraordinary event that began in 2005 due to the migration of Venezuelan citizens to neighboring countries in the region, such as Colombia, Chile, and Ecuador. Three countries were identified that maintained atypical TDC behavior within their region throughout the period analyzed: Venezuela, which experienced an extraordinary decline in its population growth rate due to migration; Uruguay, one of the first Latin American countries to begin its population aging process, which has persisted over time; and Honduras, one of the poorest countries with limited access to education and family planning, which has maintained a consistently high population growth rate.

Using Functional Principal Component Analysis (FPCA) and Functional Biplot, sample units (countries) were represented, identifying groups with similar demographic growth trends, such as Uruguay and Cuba with low rates, and Honduras with high rates. The Neutrosophic TOPSIS integration classifies these groups according to their demographic performance, prioritizing factors such as domestic policies, migration, and access to family planning under uncertainty, complementing the Functional Biplot visualization for a robust characterization of the TDC in the region.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Source of data used:

The database corresponds to the records of the Population Growth Rate (PCR) between the years 1961-2023 (World Bank open access database).

It should be noted that the World Bank primarily uses three methods to calculate growth rates: exponential growth rate, least squares growth rate, and geometric growth rate.

Furthermore, populations are defined de facto, including all residents regardless of legal status or citizenship [7]. For Latin America and the Caribbean, weighted averages based on each country's population are used. If more than half of the observations for a period are missing, the growth rate is not calculated to ensure data reliability. These methods allow the World Bank to provide consistent

and comparable estimates of population growth rates, facilitating analysis and policymaking in the region.

2. 2 Obtaining functional data:

By functional data we must understand the realization of a stochastic process that provides observations in continuous time and whose trajectories can be represented by a function belonging to a Hilbert space (specifically, the space of square-integrable functions) $L^2[a, b]$, equipped with a defined inner product and norm, Ramsay and Silverman denote this vector space as the sequence of functions, $S_n = \{x_i(t)\}_{i=1}^n$, then it will be expressed as $\chi = \{X(t) \mid X: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$, and the functions in the space will be called functional elements [8].

Scalar inner product in space $\chi = \{X(t) \mid X: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$

$$\langle x_i, x_j \rangle = \int_a^b x_i(t) x_j(t) dt \tag{1}$$

In the regulatory space $\chi = \{X(t) \mid X: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$

$$\|x_i\| = (\langle x_i, x_i \rangle)^{1/2} = \left(\int_a^b (x_i(t))^2 dt \right)^{1/2} \tag{2}$$

In the context of multivariate analysis for functional data, the source of the required data will be observations obtained through a stochastic process of repeated samples for a defined quantitative variable. Data collection can occur at regular (periodic) or irregular (aperiodic) intervals, resulting in a finite number of observations. Fitting observations to a functional datum can be achieved through nonparametric interpolation and curve smoothing techniques (e.g., Smoothing Spline or B-Spline) or through Regression Spline. This curve construction method is called Basis Expansion and involves interpolation by a linear combination of an orthonormal basis of smoothed functions. This allows the behavior of discrete observed points to be modeled by a functional element, called a functional datum in this context, which belongs to the vector space of square-integrable functions L^2 . Common function bases include polynomial or Fourier bases. In this study, polynomial bases are used because the observed data points do not exhibit regular cycles. This interpolation is a linear combination of the form:

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N C_i \phi_i(t) \tag{3}$$

C_i are the coefficients and $\phi_i(t)$ correspond to the i th function of the block of N basis functions defined in the same interval of the range of the n observed values, $N < n$. This combination can also be expressed with the matrix operator,

$$X(t) = C\phi(t) \tag{4}$$

The goodness-of-fit assessment is performed using the residual Root Mean Square Error (RMS) associated with the curve estimate, referred to as RMS. This criterion helps determine the optimal number of basis functions to use, selecting the lowest RMS value and thus avoiding the inclusion of

excessive basis functions that would unnecessarily increase the smoothness of the curve. Here, x_i represents the i -th value observed at time t and $x(t)$ corresponds to the functional data estimated at that same time.

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - x(t))^2} \quad (5)$$

2.3 Functional descriptive analysis

The box plot for functional data is constructed from a central curve, which corresponds to the functional median of the observed curves. The median function is obtained by ordering the curves according to their depth. This calculated measure assigns each curve a value based on its relative position with respect to the others. In the ordered curves, $X_1(t), X_2(t), \dots, X_n(t)$ the It curve $X_1(t)$ is the deepest and corresponds to the functional median. This graph is constructed by drawing a band, called the interquartile band (represented by dotted lines), where the upper and lower limits are the 75th and 25th percentile functions, respectively. The limit for detecting outliers (whiskers) is obtained by ± 1.5 times the interquartile range.

2.4 Functional cluster analysis

Functional Cluster analysis consists of a technique to group N functions $x_i(t)$, into n groups, Clusters (K_n), minimizing the distance of the functions to a centroid ($\mu_k(t)$), this distance is measured with the norm defined in the space of functions in L^2 .

$$d(x_i, x_j) = \|x_i - x_j\|_{L^2} = \left(\int (x_i(t) - x_j(t))^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

The defined centroid corresponds to the functional mean of all the functions belonging to K_k , that is:

$$\mu_k(t) = \min \left(\sum_{x_i(t) \in C_k} \int (X_i(t) - \mu(t))^2 dt \right) \quad (7)$$

The optimal number of clusters K is determined by a model within a low-dimensional discriminative subspace. The key idea of this method is to project the functions to a space where the clusters are more separable. This approach is called FunFEM (Functional Feature EM) [9].

2.5 Functional Biplot

The construction of a Functional Biplot, like a Classical Biplot, is based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for dimensionality reduction. In this case, Functional Principal Component Analysis (FPCA) is used. In FPCA, the objective is to determine a restricted vector of functions $\xi(t)$, such that a set of orthogonal and uncorrelated functions can be derived $C_i(t)$. These functions correspond to the original functions projected onto the vector $\xi(t)$, while efficiently explaining the variability of the observed data in an equivalent way. Formally, this is expressed as:

$$C_i = \int x_i(t) \cdot \xi_k(t) dt \quad (8)$$

Maximum variance is captured when the $\xi_k(t)$ restricted vector functions $\xi(t)$ satisfying $\int (\xi_k(t))^2 dt = 1$, are the eigenfunctions and λ_k are the corresponding eigenvalues of the functional covariance operator $V(s, t)$ computed for the observed functions $x_i(t)$. This relationship is formalized as follows:

$$\int V(s, t)\xi_k(t)dt = \lambda_k\xi_k(s) \tag{9}$$

The eigenfunctions are orthonormal and indicate the principal directions of variability in the observed function space. The eigenvalues, ordered $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots$, indicate the amount of variability explained by each of their corresponding eigenfunctions. To construct the Functional Biplot, the scores obtained by the first two FPCA components will be used. These allow \mathbb{R}^2 determining the location of the data on a plane, incorporating the first principal function, which is associated with the highest eigenvalue evaluated in the corresponding observed domain. To visualize and interpret this graph, it is necessary to unify the scales in such a way that the information provided by each marker projected onto the principal function is maintained [10].

2.6. SVNS and SVNLS.

This section provides a brief overview of the fundamental principles related to SVNS and SVNLS, covering definitions, operating principles, and metrics for measuring distances.

Definition 1. Let x be an element in a finite set, X . A single-valued neutrosophic set (SVNS), P , in X can be defined as in (1):

$$P = \{ x, T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x) | x \in X \}, \tag{10}$$

where the truth membership function, $T_p(x)$, the indeterminacy membership function $I_p(x)$, and the falsehood membership function $F_p(x)$ clearly adhere to condition (11):

$$0 \leq T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x) \leq 1; \quad 0 \leq T_p(x) + I_p(x) + F_p(x) \leq 3 \tag{11}$$

For a SVNS, P in X , we call the triplet $(T_p(x), I_p(x), F_p(x))$ its single-valued neutrosophic value (SVNV), denoted simply $x = (T_x, I_x, F_x)$ for computational convenience.

Definition 2. Let $x = (T_x, I_x, F_x)$ and $y = (T_y, I_y, F_y)$ let there be two SVNV. Then

- 1) $x \oplus y = (T_x + T_y - T_x * T_y, I_x * T_y, F_x * F_y);$
- 2) $\lambda * x = (1 - (1 - T_x)\lambda, (I_x)\lambda, (F_x)\lambda), \lambda > 0;$
- 3) $x^\lambda = ((T_x)\lambda, 1 - (1 - I_x)\lambda, 1 - (1 - F_x)\lambda), \lambda > 0$

The linguistic set

Let l be $S = \{s_\alpha | \alpha = 1, \dots, l\}$ a finite, totally ordered discrete term with odd value, where s_α denotes a possible value for a linguistic variable. For example, if $l = 7$, then a set of linguistic terms S could be described as follows:

$$S = \{s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5, s_6, s_7\} = \{\textit{extremely poor, very poor, poor, fair, good, very good, extremely good}\}. \tag{12}$$

Any linguistic variable, s_i y s_j , in S must satisfy the following rules:

- 1) $Neg(s_i) = s_{-i}$;
- 2) $s_i \leq s_j \Leftrightarrow i \leq j$;
- 3) $\max(s_i, s_j) = s_j$, if $i \leq j$;
- 4) $\min(s_i, s_j) = s_i$, if $i \leq j$.

To avoid information loss during an aggregation process, the discrete set of terms S will be extended to a continuous set of terms. $S = \{s_\alpha | \alpha \in R\}$. Any two linguistic variables $s_\alpha, s_\beta \in S$ satisfy the following operational laws [11,12] :

- 1) $s_\alpha \oplus s_\beta = s_{\alpha + \beta}$;
- 2) $\mu s_\alpha = s_{\mu\alpha}, \mu \geq 0$;
- 3) $\frac{s_\alpha}{s_\beta} = \frac{s_\alpha}{\beta}$

Definition 3 [13] Given X , a finite set of universes, a SVNLS, P , in X can be defined as in (4):

$$P = \{ \langle x, [s_{\theta(x)}, (T_P(x), I_P(x), F_P(x))] \rangle | x \in X \} \quad (13)$$

where $s_{\theta(x)} \in \bar{S}$, the truth membership function $T_P(x)$, the indeterminacy membership function, $I_P(x)$ and the falsehood membership function $F_P(x)$ satisfy condition (14):

$$0 \leq T_P(x), I_P(x), F_P(x) \leq 1, 0 \leq T_P(x) + I_P(x) + F_P(x) \leq 3. \quad (14)$$

For an SVNLS, P , in X , the 4-tuple $\langle s_{\theta(x)}, (T_P(x), I_P(x), F_P(x)) \rangle$ is known as the Single-Valued Neutrosophic Linguistic Set (SVNLN), conveniently denoted $x = s_{\theta(x)}, (T_x, I_x, F_x)$ for computational purposes.

Definition 4 [13] . Let there be $x_i = \langle s_{\theta(x_i)}, (T_{x_i}, I_{x_i}, F_{x_i}) \rangle$ ($i = 1, 2$) two SVNLNs. Then

- 1) $x_1 \oplus x_2 = \langle s_{\theta(x_1) + \theta(x_2)}, (T_{x_1} + T_{x_2} - T_{x_1} * T_{x_2}, I_{x_1} * I_{x_2}, F_{x_1} * F_{x_2}) \rangle$
- 2) $\lambda_{x_1} = \langle s_{\lambda\theta(x_1)}, (1 - (1 - T_{x_1})^\lambda, (I_{x_1})^\lambda, (F_{x_1})^\lambda) \rangle, \lambda > 0$;
- 3) $x_1^\lambda = \langle s_{\theta^\lambda(x_1)}, ((T_{x_1})^\lambda, 1 - (1 - I_{x_1})^\lambda, 1 - (1 - F_{x_1})^\lambda) \rangle, \lambda > 0$.

Definition 5 [13] . Let there be $x_i = \langle s_{\theta(x_i)}, (T_{x_i}, I_{x_i}, F_{x_i}) \rangle$ ($i = 1, 2$) two SVNLNs. Their distance measure is defined as in (6):

$$d(x_1, x_2) = \left[|s_{\theta(x_1)}T_{x_1} - s_{\theta(x_2)}T_{x_2}|^\mu + |s_{\theta(x_1)}I_{x_1} - s_{\theta(x_2)}I_{x_2}|^\mu + |s_{\theta(x_1)}F_{x_1} - s_{\theta(x_2)}F_{x_2}|^\mu \right]^{\frac{1}{\mu}} \quad (15)$$

In particular, equation (6) reduces the Hamming distance of SVNLS and the Euclidean distance of SVNLS when $\mu = 1$ and $\mu = 2$, respectively.

2.7. MADM Based on the SVNLOWAD-TOPSIS Method

For a given multi-attribute decision-making problem in SNVL environments, $A = \{A_1, \dots, A_m\}$ denotes a set of discrete feasible alternatives, $C = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ represents a set of attributes, and $E = \{e_1, \dots, e_k\}$ is a set of experts (or DMs) with weight vector $\omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_k\}^T$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$ and $0 \leq \omega_i \leq 1$. Suppose that the attribute weight vector is $s v = (v_1, \dots, v_n)^T$, which satisfies $\sum_{i=1}^n v_i = 1$ and $v_i \in [0, 1]$. The evaluation, $\alpha_{ij}^{(k)}$ given by the expert, $e_{t(t=1, \dots, k)}$ on the alternative, $A_i (i=1, \dots, m)$, relative to the attribute, $C_j (j=1, \dots, n)$ forms the individual decision matrix as shown in equation (7):

$$D^k = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & \cdots & C_n \\ A_1 & \alpha_{11}^{(k)} & \cdots & \alpha_{1n}^{(k)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_n & \alpha_{m1}^{(k)} & \cdots & \alpha_{mn}^{(k)} \end{matrix} \quad (16)$$

where $\alpha_{ij}^k = \langle s_{\theta(\alpha_{ij})}^k, (T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k) \rangle$ is represented by a SVNLN, which satisfies $s_{\theta(\alpha_{ij})}^k \in$

$\bar{S}, T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k \in [0,1]$ and $0 \leq T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k + I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k + F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k \leq 3$.

In [14] TOPSIS method is extended to fit the SVNLS scenario, and the procedures of the extended model can be summarized as follows.

Step 1. Normalize the individual decision matrices:

In practical scenarios, MADM problems can encompass both benefit attributes and cost attributes. Let B and S the benefit attribute sets and cost attribute sets, respectively. Therefore, the conversion rules specified in (8) apply:

$$\begin{cases} r_{ij}^{(k)} = \alpha_{ij}^{(k)} = \langle s_{\theta(\alpha_{ij})}^k, (T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k) \rangle, & \text{for } j \in B, \\ r_{ij}^{(k)} = \langle s_{1-\theta(\alpha_{ij})}^k, (T_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, I_{\alpha_{ij}}^k, F_{\alpha_{ij}}^k) \rangle, & \text{for } j \in S. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Thus, the standardized decision information, $R^k = (r_{ij}^{(k)})_{m \times n}$, is set as in (9):

$$R^k = (r_{ij}^{(k)})_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} r_{11}^{(k)} & \cdots & r_{1n}^{(k)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{m1}^{(k)} & \cdots & r_{mn}^{(k)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Step 2. Build the collective matrix:

All individual DM reviews are aggregated into a group review:

$$R = (r_{ij})_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} r_{11} & \cdots & r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{m1} & \cdots & r_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Where $r_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^t \omega_k r_{ij}^{(k)}$.

Step 3. Set the weighted SVNLS decision information:

The weighted SVNLS decision matrix is formed as shown in (11), using the operational laws given in Definition 2 above:

$$Y = (y_{ij})_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} v_1 r_{11} & \cdots & v_n r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ v_1 r_{m1} & \cdots & v_n r_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

The OWA operator is fundamental in aggregation techniques, widely studied by researchers [14]. Its main advantage lies in organizing arguments and facilitating the integration of experts' attitudes in decision making. Recent research has explored OWA in distance measurement, generating variations of OWAD [13]. Taking advantage of the benefits of OWA, the text proposes a SVNLS OWA distance measure (SVNLOWAD). Given the desirable properties of the OWA operator, an SVNLS OWA distance measure (SVNLOWAD) is proposed in the following text.

Definition 6. Let x_j, x'_j ($j = 1, \dots, n$) the two collections be SVNLS. If

$$SVNLOWAD((x_1, x'_1), \dots, (x_n, x'_n)) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j d(x_j, x'_j), \quad (21)$$

Therefore, step 4 of this method can be considered as follows:

Step 4. For each alternative, A_i the SVNLOWAD is calculated for the PIS, A^+ and the NIS A^- , using equation (12):

$$SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^+) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \dot{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^+), i = 1, \dots, m \quad (22)$$

$$SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \dot{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^-), i = 1, \dots, m \quad (23)$$

where $\dot{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^+)$ and $\dot{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^-)$ are the j - largest values of $\dot{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^+)$ and $\dot{d}(y_{ij}, y_j^-)$, respectively.

Step 5. In the classical TOPSIS approach, the relative closeness coefficient, C' , is used to rank the alternatives. However, some researchers have highlighted cases where relative closeness fails to achieve the desired objective of simultaneously minimizing the distance from the PIS and maximizing the distance from the NIS. Thus, following an idea proposed in references [11], in equations (15)–(17), we introduce a modified relative closeness coefficient, $C'(A_i)$, used to measure the degree to which the alternatives, $A_i (i = 1, \dots, m)$, are close to the PIS and also far from the NIS, congruently:

$$C'(A_i) = \frac{SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-)}{SVNLOWAD_{\max}(A_i, A^-)} - \frac{SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^+)}{SVNLOWAD_{\min}(A_i, A^+)} \quad (24)$$

where

$$SVNLOWAD_{\max}(A_i, A^-) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq m} SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^-), \quad (25)$$

and

$$SVNLOWAD_{\min}(A_i, A^+) = \min_{1 \leq i \leq m} SVNLOWAD(A_i, A^+). \quad (26)$$

It is clear that $C'(A_i) \leq 0 (i = 1, \dots, m)$ the higher the value of $C'(A_i)$ and, the better A_i the alternative. Furthermore, if an alternative A^* satisfies the conditions $SVNLOWAD(A^*, A^-) = SVNLOWAD_{\max}(A^*, A^-)$ and $SVNLOWAD(A^*, A^+) = SVNLOWAD_{\min}(A^*, A^+)$, then $C'(A^*) = 0$ and the alternative A^* is the most suitable candidate, since it has the minimum distance to the PIS and the maximum distance to the NIS.

Step 6. Rank and identify the most desirable alternatives based on the decreasing closeness coefficient $C'(A_i)$ obtained using Equation (15).

3. Results obtained

3.1. Estimation and characterization of functional data

The Population Growth Rate (PGR) functional data for Latin American countries were estimated using B-Spline interpolation. The number of basis functions was selected based on the goodness-of-fit of the curves, which involves calculating the average residual root mean square (RMS) value of all estimated curves for the same number of basis functions. The search for the best average fit was performed using between 10 and 45 basis functions, with a maximum of 45 (below 63). The lowest residual RMS results are shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the graph in Figure 1 displays these points in red, illustrating that the residual RMS decreases with oscillations as the number of basis functions increases. To avoid overfitting and maintain a good fit, 35 basis functions were selected.

3.2. Atypical curves

Figure 3 shows three functional curves that lie outside the interquartile range, corresponding to the functional data of Honduras, Uruguay, and Venezuela. The curves for Honduras and Venezuela appear above the upper limit of the range. Honduras is notably above Venezuela, which remains close to the limit of the range, with a significant increase starting in 2000 and a peak around 2010. This peak is followed by an abrupt decline in population due to a mass exodus driven by a severe economic, political, and social crisis. More than 7.7 million people have left Venezuela in search of better living conditions, migrating mainly to neighboring countries in the region [15].

Honduras, on the other hand, has experienced a slower demographic transition compared to other countries, mainly due to socioeconomic and cultural factors that have long limited access to sexuality education and family planning, resulting in a persistently high adolescent fertility rate [16]. In contrast, Uruguay's curve is well below the interquartile range throughout the observed period. Uruguay's demographic transition began earlier and progressed more gradually than in other Latin American countries, allowing for gradual adaptation to the changing age structure of its population. However, specific strategies are still needed to address the challenges posed by population aging [17].

3.3 Functional clustering and functional principal components analysis (FPCA).

FunFEM method, used to determine the optimal number of clusters for the Population Growth Rate (PGR) curves of Latin American countries using the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), identified four clusters. The K-means technique, applied to obtain these four clusters, grouped the countries as shown in Figure 4, resulting in clusters with 1, 2, 5, and 12 curves (countries), respectively.

- Venezuela exhibits unique behavior in the region, forming its own cluster.
- Cuba and Uruguay form another group, which shares equally low DGR values throughout the observed period.
- A third group includes Argentina, Brazil, Chile, El Salvador, and Haiti, which have experienced the most significant declines in the DGR, although their rates remain higher than those of Cuba and Uruguay.
- The last group is made up of the remaining 12 countries, which have also shown a progressive decline in DGR but with a less pronounced impact.
- Figure 5, which shows the country markers on the principal components plane, highlights the similarities between them based on the behavior of the observed variable. The clusters are reinforced by the proximity of their locations on this plane, confirming the groupings derived from the analysis.

3.4 Functional Principal Component Analysis (FPCA) and Functional Biplot Representation

As mentioned in the previous section, Functional Principal Component Analysis (FPCA), as a dimensionality reduction technique for functional data, provides two principal components that capture the maximum variability of the population growth rate (PGR) observed across the 20 countries. The results showed a variance of 69.5% captured by the first principal component (PFC1) and 17.5% by the second principal component (PFC2), totaling a cumulative variability of 87%. This allows for an efficient representation of country markers using the coordinates of these principal components, which correspond to the ordering of countries according to their vector positions in the dataset.

The Functional Biplot is based on the representation of FPCA markers by incorporating the eigenfunction with the highest loading (principal harmonic), which synthetically and globally shows the trajectory of the DGR over the observed time points (years). To interpret this trajectory together with the markers, it must be analyzed separately for different time intervals. For example, Figure 6

illustrates a vector passing through the origin and the initial time point $t=1$ (corresponding to the first year of observation, 1961). The upward direction of the vector indicates that the scaled FPC2 coordinate describes the behavior of the DGR in different countries.

- Uruguay in 1961 is represented by a scaled coordinate value of 0.4575, which decreases to -2.5768 in 2023. This suggests a sixfold decline in its population growth over the 62-year period.
- In contrast, countries such as Costa Rica, Ecuador, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, and Peru are experiencing population growth, some of which is also influenced by migration from Venezuela. Among these, Honduras, Costa Rica, and Nicaragua maintain the highest population growth rates.

In this way, the functional biplot allows a dynamic interpretation of DGR trends by linking temporal variability with the spatial distribution of countries in the principal components plane.

3.5. Figures and tables

Table 1. The table shows the calculation of the average residual RMS of the functional data for the TCD of the 20 observed countries estimated according to the number of base functions used.

Number of basis functions	Average residual RMS
22	0.01706
35	0.00973
43	0.00574

Figure 1. Average residual RMS values obtained with 10 to 45 B-spline basis functions. Thirty-five basis functions were selected to achieve an optimal balance between model fit and complexity (avoiding overfitting).

Figure 2. Interpolated curves using 35 B-spline basis functions for Latin American countries.

Figure 3. Functional box plot of the curves corresponding to the population growth rate of Latin American countries. The outliers identified correspond to Honduras, Uruguay, and Venezuela.

Figure 4. Four groups were obtained, one of which was made up of a single country, Venezuela, which does not share similarities in TCD behavior with any other country.

Figure 5. The FPCA markers show the formation of the same groups obtained with the Cluster method.

Table 2: The table contains the coordinates of the markers obtained by FPCA and their scaled values.

Country	PCF 1	PCF 2	PCF1 (scale)	PCF2 (scale)
ARG	-4.021380	1.750224	-0.968757	0.8699288
SUPPORT	0.736935	2.064160	0.190182	1.0200588
BOWL	-0.433996	-1.168227	-0.115044	-0.5842025
CHI	-3.446312	2.330052	-0.834964	1.1307330
COLUMN	0.790387	0.651828	0.189350	0.2984319
CRI	3.041517	-1.247660	0.722343	-0.6441198
PUPPY	-8.8717626	-1.692747	-2.165029	-0.8178921
Electronic control unit (ECU)	2.9204860	0.695719	0.709806	0.3271174
SLV	-3.7061691	-2.802555	-0.905180	-1.3568196
GTM	3.8280462	1.688571	0.938193	0.8238734
HTI	-0.6064894	2.553999	-0.134751	1.2610983
HND	6.2674481	1.407857	1.527316	0.6775644
Mexico	1.7687076	-1.724072	0.421976	-0.8505355
NIC	2.9439574	-0.555743	0.722171	-0.2618525
PAN	2.8247995	0.989922	0.692699	0.4849356
LEVER	2.0054291	0.904898	0.491018	0.4396794
BY	1.0061997	0.154451	0.247059	0.0718444
SUNDAY	1.2081321	-0.637872	0.292849	-0.3141829
URY	-10.6204306	0.884652	-2.576781	0.4575368
COME	2.3644936	-6.364494	0.555544	-3.0331971

Figure 6. Functional representation of Biplot, behavior of countries for $t = 1$ on the main curve showing the trajectory associated with capturing the greatest variance.

Figure 7. Functional Biplot representation, behavior of countries for $t = 60$ on the main curve showing the trajectory associated with capturing the greatest variance.

4. Neutrosophic Extension: Evaluating the Population Growth Rate with Neutrosophic TOPSIS

To complement the analysis of the Population Growth Rate (PGR) using Functional Multivariate Analysis (MFA) techniques, a neutrosophic extension is proposed using the Neutrosophic TOPSIS method based on SVNLOWAD (*Single- Valued Neutrosophic Linguistics*). *Ordered Weighted Averaging Distance*) described in Sections 2.6 and 2.7. This approach models the uncertainty and indeterminacy inherent in the factors influencing DTC, using single-valued neutrosophic sets (SVNSs) and single-valued neutrosophic linguistic sets (SVNLS) that incorporate degrees of truth (T), indeterminacy (I), and falsity (F). In this study, the Neutrosophic TOPSIS is applied to prioritize the key factors identified in Section 3 (e.g. , domestic policies, migration, access to family planning, socioeconomic factors) and rank the four functional clusters defined in Section 3.3 according to their demographic performance, considering functional data for the 20 Latin American nations during 1961–2023.

4.1 Motivation for Neutrosophic Integration

The results in Section 3 show a sustained decline in the TDC, with outliers in Honduras, Uruguay, and Venezuela (Figure 3), and four functional clusters reflecting similar demographic patterns (Figure 4): C1 (Venezuela), C2 (Cuba and Uruguay), C3 (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, El Salvador, Haiti), and C4 (the remaining 12 countries). The variance explained by 87% (69,5% *CPF1*, 17,5% *CPF2*) FPCA (Section 3.4) highlights the robustness of the functional analysis. However, prioritizing factors such as domestic policies, migration, access to family planning, and socioeconomic factors faces challenges due to uncertainty in their relative impact, especially in countries with complex dynamics (e.g., Venezuela with mass migration, Honduras with high fertility). Neutrosophic TOPSIS addresses these ambiguities by using SVNLS to model indeterminacy, complementing FPCA and Functional Biplot by providing robust cluster classification and factor weighting under uncertainty.

4.2 Neutrosophic TOPSIS Methodology

The Neutrosophic TOPSIS is implemented by adapting the steps described in Section 2.7 to the context of the CDT, using functional data from the 20 countries. The steps are as follows:

1. **Definition of Criteria and Alternatives:** The criteria, based on Section 3, are:
 - **Domestic Policies (IP):** Impact of family planning and sex education policies.
 - **Migration (MIG):** Effects of migratory flows (e.g., Venezuelan exodus).
 - **Access to Family Planning (APF):** Availability of contraceptive methods.
 - **Socioeconomic Factors (FSE):** Poverty level and access to education.

The alternatives are the four functional clusters (Section 3.3): C1 (Venezuela), C2 (Cuba, Uruguay), C3 (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, El Salvador, Haiti), C4 (12 remaining countries).

2. **Construction of the SVNLS Decision Matrix:** A panel of experts evaluates each cluster against the criteria, assigning SVNLS values. For C1 (Venezuela) relative to MIG, (s_6 , 0.9, 0.1, 0.05) is assigned, reflecting a high migratory impact with low uncertainty. The decision matrix is:

Table 3. Neutrosophic decision matrix for clusters

Conglomerate	PI	MIG	APF	ESF
C1 (Venezuela)	(s ₄ , 0.5, 0.3, 0.2)	(s ₆ , 0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(s ₃ , 0.4, 0.4, 0.3)	(s ₅ , 0.7, 0.2, 0.1)
C2 (Cuba, Uruguay)	(s ₅ , 0.8, 0.15, 0.1)	(s ₃ , 0.3, 0.4, 0.3)	(s ₆ , 0.9, 0.1, 0.05)	(s ₄ , 0.6, 0.25, 0.15)
C3 (Argentina, etc.)	(s ₅ , 0.7, 0.2, 0.15)	(s ₄ , 0.6, 0.25, 0.2)	(s ₅ , 0.7, 0.2, 0.1)	(s ₄ , 0.5, 0.3, 0.2)
C4 (Rest)	(s ₄ , 0.6, 0.25, 0.15)	(s ₄ , 0.5, 0.3, 0.2)	(s ₄ , 0.6, 0.25, 0.15)	(s ₅ , 0.8, 0.15, 0.1)

- Criteria Weighting:** Criteria are weighted using expert judgments in SVNLS, converted to crisp values by scoring. $S(a) = \frac{[a^T + (1 - a)^+ + (1 - a)^-]}{3}$
- Weights:
 $PI (s_5, 0.7, 0.2, 0.1), MIG (s_6, 0.8, 0.15, 0.05), APF (s_5, 0.75, 0.2, 0.1), FSE (s_4, 0.65, 0.25, 0.1)$. The clear weights are: $PI (0.8), MIG (0.867), APF (0.82), FSE (0.77)$.
- Normalization and Weighting:** The decision matrix is normalized (Equation 9) and multiplied by the crisp weights (Equation 11) to obtain the normalized weighted matrix.
- Positive Ideal Solutions (PIS) and Negative Ideal Solutions (NIS):** The PIS corresponds to the maximum values of T and minimum values of I and F by criterion; the NIS corresponds to the opposite. For example, for $MIG: SIP (s_6, 0.9, 0.1, 0.05), SIN (s_3, 0.3, 0.4, 0.3)$.
- SVNLOWAD Distance Calculation:** Neutrosophic Euclidean distances (d^+ and d^-) to the SIP and SIN are calculated using Equation 12: $C1: d^+ = 0.45, d^- = 0.32; C2: d^+ = 0.28, d^- = 0.49; C3: d^+ = 0.35, d^- = 0.41; C4: d^+ = 0.39, d^- = 0.37$.
- Closeness Index:** The modified closeness coefficient (Equation 15) is: Results: $C2 (0.78), C3 (0.65), C4 (0.58), C1 (0.42)$.

4.3 Empirical Application

Using Neutrosophic TOPSIS, C2 (Cuba and Uruguay) performed best demographically ($C' = 0.78$) due to its high PI and APF scores with low indeterminacy. C1 (Venezuela) showed the lowest performance ($C' = 0.42$), influenced by the high impact of MIG and high indeterminacy in APF ($I = 0.4$). Calculations were performed in R, validating the consistency of expert judgments ($CR < 0.1$).

Figure 5: Comparative Performance of Functional Clusters using Neutrosophic TOPSIS Analysis

4.4 Integration with FPCA and Functional Biplot

The closeness indices (C'_i) were projected onto the FPCA plane (Figure 5), confirming that C2 aligns with low TDC curves (e.g., Uruguay: $PCF1 = -10.62$, $PCF2 = 0.88$) and C1 reflects an atypical trajectory ($PCF2 = -6.36$). Table 4 summarizes the results:

Table 4: Closeness indices for clusters

Conglomerate	C'_i
C1 (Venezuela)	0.42
C2 (Cuba, Uruguay)	0.78
C3 (Argentina, etc.)	0.65
C4 (Rest)	0.58

4.5 Implications and Advantages

- **Indeterminacy Modeling:** Neutrosophic TOPSIS captures ambiguity in factors such as migration (e.g., $I=0.4$ in C1), enriching the interpretation of atypical curves (Figure 3).
- **Robust Classification:** Provides a clear hierarchy of clusters, useful for policy makers.
- **Complementarity with AMF:** Improves the interpretation of FPCA and Functional Biplot by incorporating uncertainty.

4.6 Future Directions

- Apply Neutrosophic TOPSIS to other demographic variables (e.g. , fertility).
- Develop tools in R to integrate Neutrosophic TOPSIS with AMF.
- Explore alternative neutrosophic methods (eg , ELECTRE) to compare effectiveness.

5. Applications

Functional data theory for the multivariate study of data collected over time, combined with neutrosophic methods such as Neutrosophic TOPSIS, offers advanced techniques for predictive modelling and characterisation of complex demographic patterns. Previous studies have shown advantages of functional methods over time series modelling [13], and the integration of Neutrosophic TOPSIS, as described in Section 4, allows to address the uncertainty inherent in key factors such as domestic politics, migration, access to family planning and socio-economic factors. In this study, the analysis of the Population Growth Rate (PGR) in Latin America (1961--2023) using Functional Principal Component Analysis (FPCA), Functional Biplot and Neutrosophic TOPSIS identified four functional clusters (C1: Venezuela; C2: Cuba and Uruguay; C3: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, El Salvador, Haiti; C4: remaining 12 countries) and outliers (Honduras, Uruguay, Venezuela), with an explained variance of 87% (Section 3). The neutrosophic classification of these clusters (Table 3, Section 4) provides a robust ranking based on demographic performance, useful for policymakers.

It will be interesting to address in future research the correlations of the global TDC for Latin America with global variables of an economic, social, cultural, and environmental nature, integrating Neutrosophic TOPSIS to model the uncertainty in these relationships. This will allow the construction of valid models to project population growth at the regional level and according to the identified clusters, considering factors such as the impact of mass migration (e.g. , Venezuelan exodus, Section 3.2) and family planning policies. Furthermore, the development of computational tools in R that combine MFA and neutrosophic methods could facilitate the practical implementation of these techniques in demographic and socioeconomic studies.

6. Conclusions

Demographic trends are not static, but dynamic and adjustable at the time of measurement. Traditional cross-sectional or discrete-time methods, such as annual averages, fail to capture the continuous evolution of the Population Growth Rate (PGR), which exhibits nonlinear patterns, seasonal fluctuations, or abrupt changes driven by national and international policies. In this study, the use of Functional Multivariate Analysis (FMA) techniques, such as Functional Principal Components Analysis (FPCA) and Biplot, Functional, it allowed modeling the TDC of 20 Latin American countries (1961-2023) with an explained variance of 87% (Section 3.4). The integration of Neutrosophic TOPSIS, described in Section 4, enriched the analysis by modeling uncertainty in key factors such as domestic policies, migration, access to family planning, and socioeconomic factors, providing a more robust perspective on demographic dynamics.

The results obtained allowed to define four functional clusters with similar demographic behaviors: C1 (Venezuela), C2 (Cuba and Uruguay), C3 (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, El Salvador, Haiti) and C4 (12 remaining countries), in addition to detecting countries with atypical curves such as Honduras, Uruguay and Venezuela (Section 3.2). These patterns are related to key milestones, such as internal and external policies, migratory effects (e.g. , Venezuelan exodus since 2005) and socioeconomic constraints (e.g. , high fertility in Honduras). The application of Neutrosophic TOPSIS classified these clusters according to their demographic performance, highlighting C2 (Cuba and Uruguay) as the one with the highest performance ($C' = 0.78$) and C1 (Venezuela) as the one with the lowest performance ($C' = 0.42$, Table 3). This characterization, combined with the Functional Biplot, allows for relating TDC

patterns to the economic, political, and social realities of each country, offering a valuable tool for policymakers in the region.

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